

ISic2941

I.Sicily inscription 2941

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG2002

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332184

1. [— — —]ω [— — — — —]

2. [—(?)—] vacat

3. [— — —] τῶν ἰδίων [— —]

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644850

EDCS 70900011

PHI 332184

Bibliography

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